

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING ROLE PLAYING IN TEACHING

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Annotation: this article is devoted to the method of using role-playing games in the process of *teaching foreign languages to students*.

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Introduction.

Getting a child interested in a foreign language and giving information about it is also a very difficult task. In this regard, the methods used during the lesson, the system of methods used are important. Not only these methods but his alertness and dedication too are most required. Knowing the language means knowing the hand. The phrase has become quite popular over the years. But learning a language also takes a lot of effort. We definitely need to use a path that is effective and easy for us to learn a foreign language perfectly. As we know technologies can be used differently at different stages of the lesson, depending on the purpose of the topic and the content of the topic. A number of different technologies have been developed that are very effective in teaching science, taking into account the age characteristics of schoolchildren. According to experts, the main types of human activity are formed in three ways: work, play and study. They are all interrelated. It is argued that the laws governing the formation of children's mental activity based on school learning materials are incorporated into some activities¹.

One such method is the use of role-playing games in this lesson. Nowadays; the roleplaying method is widely used throughout the lesson. At first glance, you might think that this show is a waste of our time playing a role but role-playing not only means moving hands and other body parts, but also increasing children's ability to speak in a foreign language through role-playing. They can also learn how to use emotion in the process of speaking through it. Another goal of this is that children memorize the scenario in order to play a role. They get to know the meaning and content so that they can perform it beautifully. And through role-playing, everyone deeply understands the meaning of what they are saying. This causes them to begin and develop the process of thinking in a foreign language. Role-playing methods are used by students in a variety of life situations². This method is a method of demonstrating conditions by staging. Stages of the role-playing method:

1. The teacher determines the goals and results of the game on the topic and develops a role-playing script.
2. The goals and objectives of the game are explained.

¹ N.X. Avliyakov "pedagogical technology" Tashkent-2009.

² Jalolov J.J., Maxkamova S.T., Ashurov Sh.S "English language teaching methodology" Tashkent-2015 " Fan va texnologiya "publishing.

3. Allocates roles based on the purpose of the game.
4. Students play their roles and other students follow them they stand.
5. At the end of the game, ask the students how to play the role they played again.

How to organize a role-play activity?

According to scholars ideas, in order to have a role-play activity to be successful speaking exercise it is useful to know some basic principles about organizing such an activity.

1. It is important to mention that if a teacher is not convinced about the validity of using role-playing, the activity itself "will fall flat on its face just as you expected it to"
2. The educator has to be convinced that role-play is an exciting technique to use and has many benefits.
3. If the teacher is not enthusiastic about the play, the students will not as well.

Coming out of the characters given above, any teaching sequence necessitates three vital elements:

- ❖ the engage stage
- ❖ study stage
- ❖ activate stage.

In the engage stage, the teacher's task is to attract and keep learners' attention and interest in a lesson. Students' minds have to be involved and emotionally connected with a lesson, for example by a pleasant situation or a nice picture.

Then, learners need to study the new language; it may be grammar or vocabulary exercises. Having known the new item, students are given a possibility to activate both the new language and the language they have known. Learners do it when they speak freely. Having been engaged, being presented the new language and having practiced it, learners try to activate it³.

Furthermore, it is said that language teachers should not use role-plays which are too difficult or too emotionally loaded until students are used to that kind of activity. To a certain extent, starting with very simple information-gap role-plays is advisable. During the first role-play learners may be more or less inhibited, but soon they will get accustomed to role-playing. Beyond question, students will need some time to prepare for a performance and then also try out their roles privately. Depending on the learners' language level, the amount of planning time may differ. Players at this stage of an activity work in pairs or groups and discuss together what they might say. At higher levels, students do not need so much help with the language but they will need time to get into roles.

The teacher's roles in role-play

Having analyzed the definition of role-play, the organization of such an activity, its advantages and also the notion of pair and group work, another very important issue has to be explained, namely, the teacher's role in a role-play activity. One of the teacher's function is being a facilitator. As learners practice role-play they may discover that they lack words or phrases. They may need new language to be given by the educator. This role makes the teacher act as a kind of a walking dictionary, evaluating the class and offering help when it is necessary. However, if rehearsal time is long enough, offering assistance might not be required. At times, teachers may want to become involved in a speaking activity. This way they can prompt the

³ Matmurotov Z "The using of role-playing in teaching foreign languages" Молодой учёный N24 июнь 2017.

exercise, introduce new information to help the role-play along and ensure continuing student engagement in the speaking.

Role-play seems to be an important tool in teaching speaking skills. Although there is no one definition of role-play and there are some weak points about that activity, its' numerous advantages far outweigh the disadvantages. The activity gives a chance of having a rehearsal for the language one day students may be exposed to, for example ordering food at a restaurant.

Role-play as a pedagogical method to prepare students for practice

When it is investigated the theoretical and practical issues about the usage of role playing in teaching process, language teachers should know and study the points how and why role-play supports students in gaining insights into complex leadership situations. Teachers give voice to the students by illustrating their experiences in a role-playing activity involving a human resource management issue designed, performed, and evaluated as part of a management program. The results show that the role-playing supports the students by stimulating them to understand the issue from various perspectives, hence performing an overall change of perspectives. The role- playing exercise also enables the students to create a collective understanding of the situation. The active social interactions and conversations of role-playing contributed to establishing a sense of community among the students⁴.

However, the teacher must have a strategy and a clear purpose when choosing the type of role-play in order to get the most out of the role-playing at hand. In that situation learners ask themselves the following question:

Why use role-play?

It is also important that the teacher has strategies to deal with unexpected or difficult situations. For example, when students do not want to participate because they believe that the method is childish or unscientific, when students use an exaggerated demeanor, or when embarrassment or tensions between the participants is created. Such strategies can be developed by, for example, the teacher him/herself, the role-play participants, or even learned from others by acting together with a more experienced instructor during the role-play session.

The actual role-playing exercise concerns a management meeting, at which there is a discussion, relating to a specific human resource management issue at a fictitious company. The starting point is that the management team has noticed increasing levels of inefficiency and absence due to staff illness, as the company faces growing competition and reduced demand for its services. The company's main specialize in main activity being and an has decided to hire external consultants who not issues at organizations. The role-playing e management team. After the presentation and an opportunity to ask questions, the management team discusses its opinion of the consultants' proposal.

⁴ Shaxodat Pardayeva, Gulnoz Murotova, Nazira Isanova "The current state of teaching foreign languages".

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